

IMPACT OF EDMODO IN THE TEACHING-LEARNING PROCESS OF I.T. DEPARTMENT PROFESSORS

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ABSTRACT

This research paper aims to analyze the impact of the usage of the Learning Management System which is Edmodo in the teaching-learning process of the I.T. Department Professors in the College of Arts and Sciences of San Beda University. The goal of the paper is to capture feedback from the professors on their experiences and use of Edmodo in their teaching profession. This paper is an evaluation of the five-year usage from academic year 2014 to 2018 as the university is transitioning to NEO LMS beginning in academic year 2018-2019. The participants of the research include 7 full-time faculty members with teaching experience from 5 years to 25 years. The paper analyzes in detail the most reported tool used in Edmodo such as posting notes or announcements, assignments, quizzes, exams, sharing of documents, grading, forums and feedback to students. It also evaluates the LMS Performance according to the following criteria: stability, reliability, usability, appearance and speed.

KEYWORDS – Learning Management System, Edmodo, asynchronous learning

INTRODUCTION

The professors of the Information Technology (I.T.) Department of the College of Arts and Sciences (CAS) of San Beda University have been using the Learning Management System (LMS) which is Edmodo in their teaching functions to help the students in their learning. Edmodo is a web-based LMS used by the faculty to basically perform tasks such as posting announcements, assignments, grades and communicating with students.

The proponent, an Edmodo user himself and the facilitator-trainer of all the other CAS faculty members in using the said LMS, would like to evaluate its impact on the teaching-learning environment. A total of 7 full-time faculty members answered a 6-page questionnaire to gather their perceptions and feedback on the usage of the Edmodo. The author aimed to gather feedback about the faculty members' experiences in the usage of Edmodo specifically on the following criteria: stability, reliability, usability, appearance and speed.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A Learning Management System (LMS) is a set of integrated software services that organizes and supports online learning, education, and training. This software provides the user with the ability to upload course content, class administration and discussion facilities, which consequently leads to asynchronous learning. Some LMSs offer added features such as assessment tools for quizzes and exams, and progress reports [1].

There are a lot of LMSs available now that offers asynchronous learning which allows the learners to study at their own pace and time. LMS systems are known by various names including course management system (CMS), learning content management system (LCMS), virtual learning environment (VLE), virtual learning system (VLS), learning portal, or e-learning platform. [2]

Many educators in the higher education are now using different LMSs in their teaching function. They have started using systems such as Blackboard, Canvas, Edmodo, MH Connect, Moodle, Pearson Learning Studio and many more. [3].

The Learning Management Review Survey 2018 conducted at Carleton University aimed to capture feedback from LMS users about their experience and use of cuLearn which was also called Moodle 3.1.1. The survey was part of the five-year LMS review cycle after the school transitioned from WebCT to Moodle in 2014.

METHODOLOGY

The survey started with the demographic profile of the respondents followed by the eight questions that would be used to analyze the impact of Edmodo LMS in the teaching-learning environment. Question number eight had 28 items to gather data on the perceptions of the faculty members on the criteria of stability, reliability, usability, appearance and speed. The proponent computed for the mean of each of the criterion stated above before drawing the conclusions.

RESULTS

All 7 full-time faculty members of the IT Department of the CAS at San Beda University were invited to participate in the survey. The response to the survey was significant as 100 percent of the faculty members participated and they had an average of six to ten minutes' duration in completing the task.

The proponent converted the questionnaire to a Google Form and shown below are the charts for the results. The actual responses may be obtained from the link:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1RWrOItpHzQzL22E_ZmWIq3WJudcZZqfW17GU6eYQJRo/edit#responses

DISCUSSION

The demographic profile of the I.T. faculty members were as follows: they aged from 36 years old and above, 4 females and 3 males, majority are married, 6 out of 7 had a Master’s degree, served the school with the longest tenure at 26 years old, and taught both minor and major subjects in the degree program.

All the faculty members have used an LMS for the last five academic years such as Edmodo, Blackboard, Canvas, and Moodle. The tools that they regularly used include assignments garnering 100 percent followed by announcements, content / file sharing, grades, and quizzes and exams. Only 1 professor used and LMS to teach a fully online course while all of them used it to teach blended course. If ever they encounter problems in using Edmodo, they would simply search the internet or ask a colleague and figure things out on their own.

The survey was evaluated using a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The criteria for stability was evaluated using Question 8 Items 11, 15 and 25, with a mean of 4.52 which means faculty members (FMs) strongly agree that Edmodo is stable. The criteria for reliability was evaluated using Question 8 Items 1, 6, 8, 14, 16, 17, 19, 20, 21, 23 and 26, with a mean of 4.39 which means FMs agree that Edmodo is reliable. The criteria for usability was evaluated using Question 8 Items 2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 12, and 13, with a mean of 4.29 which means FMs agree that Edmodo is usable. The criteria for appearance was evaluated using Question 8 Items 7, 9, and 18, with a mean of 4.43 which means FMs agree that Edmodo is fine with its appearance. The criteria for speed was evaluated using Question 8 Item 27 with a rating of 3.71 which means FMs barely agree that Edmodo is okay with its speed. The highest mean was for the criteria for stability and the lowest was for the speed.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The outcome of this research indicates the over-all level of effectiveness of the Edmodo Learning Management System as its impact to the teaching-learning environment of the faculty members of the Information Technology Department of the College of Arts and Sciences, San Beda University. The results showed that the most reported tools used in Edmodo was posting of assignments, announcements, content / file sharing, grades, and quizzes and exams which contributed to a paperless procedure in the teaching-learning environment.

Basing on the perceptions of the faculty members, they all strongly agreed that the Edmodo LMS achieved a desirable performance based on the criteria of stability, reliability, usability, appearance and speed.

Finally, since this research was done to evaluate the use of Edmodo in the last five academic years, the proponent is one with the faculty members in saying and recommending that there is a need to migrate to a new LMS which is NEO.

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ABOUT THE CONTRIBUTOR

Dr. Diosdado M. Aler III is an experienced I.T. Professor with a demonstrated history of working in the Higher Education industry. skilled in e-learning, coaching, staff development, educational leadership, and teaching.